

THE ROLE OF SOCIAL PROTECTION IN IMPROVING THE LIVING WELL-BEING OF THE POPULATION.

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Abstract

In this scientific article, the role of social protection in improving the well-being of the population, the reforms implemented in our country, the state's management of social processes and ensuring the social rights of citizens, suggestions for increasing the well-being of the population in the regions have been developed.

Аннотация

В данной научной статье рассмотрены роль социальной защиты в повышении благосостояния населения, проводимые в нашей стране реформы, государственное управление социальными процессами и обеспечение социальных прав граждан, предложения по повышению благосостояния населения. население в регионах развито.

Аннотация

Ушбу илмий мақолада аҳолининг фаровонлигини оширишда ижтимоий ҳимоянинг ўрни, мамлакатимизда амалга оширилаётган ислохатлар, давлатнинг ижтимоий жараёнларини бошқаришдаги ва фуқароларни ижтимоий ҳуқуқларини таъминлаши, ҳудудларда аҳоли фаровонлигини ошириш бўйича таклифлар ишлаб чиқилган.

Key words: Population, enterprise, budget, pension, salary.

Ключевые слова: Население, предприятие, бюджет, пенсия, заработная плата.

Калит сўзлар: Аҳоли, корхона, бюджет, пенсия, иш ҳақи.

Introduction

The transition to a socially oriented market economy and changes in the state's social policy increase the need to pay more attention to the problem of social protection.

During this period, while the state gives its property rights to other economic entities, it also imposes part of its social obligations on them. In the current situation, it is manifested in the involvement of the labor force in commodity-money problems, the freedom to choose the type and form of one's labor activity, and the motivation of individuals from a passive subject to an activity that serves to increase the standard of living of their family.

As a result, the social sphere is adapting to the market economy, and the state is taking the main place in the management of social processes and ensuring the social rights of citizens.

The main part

The social protection policy implemented in Uzbekistan shows that it has moved away from social protection of the entire population to targeted social protection and only helps the vulnerable part of the population in need of social protection within the framework of social programs.

The diversity of sources of funding of social programs has been strengthened, and the following have been identified as their main ones:

- State budget;
- Non-budget funds;
- Enterprise funds ;
- Population funds;

An important feature of the financing of the social protection of the population is that the organization of the use of state funds is not only for the mobilization of a large part of the state funds, but also the elements related to the composition of income and expenses should be taken into account.

During the years of independence, the state's expenditures for the social sphere constantly change in harmony with the national production and the main issues being resolved in the economy. Creating all opportunities for the development of small business and private entrepreneurship and increasing the income of the population on this basis was considered as an important task.

In the social protection of the population, the state gives priority to maintaining the amount of real wages, pensions and scholarships and preventing the worsening of income inequality among the population.

In particular, in accordance with the Decree No. PF-45 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 28, 2023 "On increasing the amount of wages, pensions and allowances", from May 1, 2023, the amount of wages, pensions, scholarships and allowances of employees of budget organizations should be increased by 7 %¹.

Starting from May 1, 2023 in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan: the minimum amount of payment for labor - the minimum amount is 980,000 soums per month; the base calculation amount should be set at 330,000 soums per month.

Add the amount of allowance given to the legal representative of disabled children under 18 who needs care of others - 535,000 soums per month and 198,000 soums for each family member who is unable to work.

Summary

Today, in social protection of the population and mitigating social problems, taking into account the structural changes in the economy, it is appropriate to implement the following socio-economic measures:

- should ensure continuous growth of investment in human resources;
- in the field of employment, it is necessary to increase the competitiveness of the labor force, to improve the quality of the labor force, to create new jobs in progressive fields;
- regularly expand the measures to get rid of the feeling of poverty in social protection; it is necessary to create a system that studies the causes of the need for social protection and, on this basis, apply measures aimed at reducing it.

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¹ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PF -45 c on March 28, 2023. www . lex . en .